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Technoeconomic analysis of tethered coaxial turbines

Mehedi Hassan^{1,*}, Kenneth Granlund¹, Matthew Bryant¹, Andre Mazzoleni¹

¹Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, NC 27695, USA

Abstract

This study presents the analytical modeling of levelized cost of energy (LCOE) for a farm of coaxial dual-rotor turbines anchored to the seabed via flexible tethers for marine hydrokinetic (MHK) energy harvesting. The developed model is subsequently utilized in a bilevel optimization algorithm to determine the optimum size and number of the turbines in a deployment location for minimum LCOE. A case study is performed in the Gulf Stream off the coast of Florida to demonstrate that, for an MHK farm spanning 5 km × 5 km and situated 25.7 km offshore where the turbines are placed at a depth of 50 m below the surface in a location with a water depth of 800 m, the most cost-effective arrangement involves installing 25 turbines with a diameter of 39.33 m. This setup results in a remarkable minimum LCOE of 5.89 cents per kilowatt-hour.

Keywords: dual-rotor; levelized cost of energy; tethered; marine hydrokinetic turbines

1. Introduction

The world is evolving and so are its energy needs. In a race to combat the effects of climate change governments are investing in a wide variety of renewable energy sources [1]. One of the fastest-growing energy solutions for coastal and island countries is marine hydrokinetic (MHK) farms. Among the different types of MHK devices, tethered coaxial dual-rotor turbines (TCDT) have been gaining attention due to their potential for high efficiency and low cost [2,3]. When installing turbines in deep waters, a significant cost reduction can be attained by using tethers instead of long rigid beams to support or anchor them from the seabed because there are substantial expenses involved in constructing, installing, and maintaining such extensive structures (Fig. 1). The coaxial arrangement of the turbine rotors rotating in opposing directions allows for active torque cancellation through the generator that links them resolving tether entanglement issue [4].

As with any emerging energy generation technology, evaluating the economic feasibility of TCDTs is essential before considering their widespread commercial deployment. In the existing literature, considerable research has been conducted on assessing the LCOE for traditional single-rotor tidal turbines [5-9]. However, there is a noticeable lack of studies focusing on the technoeconomic feasibility analysis of TCDTs. This research aims to bridge this gap by introducing an analytical model specifically designed to estimate the LCOE of TCDTs. To achieve this goal, we leverage various inputs, including mass scaling laws, technical studies, industry data, market research, and a specially developed wake model designed for calculating wake velocities for dual-rotor configurations [10]. As we scale up the size of the turbine, its power extraction from the freestream also increases. However, it is crucial to strike a balance,

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: mhassan4@ncsu.edu

considering that the construction, installation, and maintenance costs also rise with size. Therefore, a genetic algorithm based on the developed model is implemented to identify the optimal size and number of turbines tailored to specific deployment sites. This analysis will facilitate informed decision-making for investors and developers by providing valuable insights into the economic viability of this new technology.

2. LCOE Optimization Algorithm

This section presents a comprehensive modeling and optimization framework for estimating the levelized cost of energy for TCDTs. To optimize the LCOE, the formulation is considered as shown in Equation 1:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } LCOE &= \frac{FCR \times CapEx + OpEx}{AEP} \\ \text{subject to:} \\ 0 &\leq x_i \leq X_{farm} \\ 0 &\leq y_i \leq Y_{farm} \\ \Delta x_i &\geq \delta x_{min} \\ \Delta y_i &\geq \delta y_{min} \\ 1 &< N \leq n_{max} \\ 0 &< d_f \leq D_{max} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. A coaxial dual-rotor turbine anchored to seabed via a flexible tether. A buoy is used for suspending the negatively buoyant turbine in mid-water.

Here, CapEx, OpEx, and AEP represent the capital expenditure, operational expenditure, and annual energy production, respectively. The fixed charge rate (FCR) refers to the yearly return expressed as a fraction of the initial capital investment, which must be achieved to satisfy investor revenue expectations. (x_i, y_i) are the position coordinates of the turbines which are constrained by the length and width of the farm X_{farm} , and Y_{farm} . $(\Delta x_i, \Delta y_i)$ are the distances between any two turbines next to each other that must be equal to or larger than a minimum distance $(\delta x_{min}, \delta y_{min})$. N is the number of turbines which ranges from 1 to a maximum range n_{max} . Lastly, d_f , which is the diameter of the front rotor, ranges from 0 to a maximum diameter value D_{max} .

Fig. 2. (a) Bilevel optimization algorithm: hill climbing algorithm (red) in external loop and genetic algorithm (blue) in the internal loop; (b)

The fitness function comprising of four modules: farm layout, CapEx, OpEx, and AEP.

To solve this optimization problem a bilevel optimization algorithm is developed involving two loops: the external hill climbing algorithm loop for optimizing the number of turbines and the internal genetic algorithm loop for

optimizing the size and layout of the turbines as shown in Fig. 2(a). A genetic algorithm (GA) is an optimization technique inspired by natural selection and genetics. It starts with a population of potential solutions, evaluates their fitness, selects the best, combines them to create new solutions, introduces occasional random changes (mutation), and repeats this process to find optimal or near-optimal solutions to complex problems. It's useful when traditional methods struggle with large or complex search spaces.

First, a random value for N , representing the number of turbines, is generated. Next, the internal GA loop is executed to determine the optimal size and layout of the farm, aiming to minimize the fitness function (LCOE) for that specific N value. Once the first GA loop is completed, a new N , denoted as N^* , is generated in the vicinity of the previous N . The GA loop is then performed again for N^* . Then the results obtained from the two loops are compared and identify which configuration yields a lower value of the fitness function. If the original N provides a lower value, another N^* is generated in the vicinity of the previous N , and the GA loop process is repeated. This iteration continues until a lower value is achieved with the newly generated N^* compared to the original N . At this point, the original N is updated to the value of N^* . Subsequently, the stopping criteria are checked. The process is continued in a loop until the criteria is fulfilled.

The proposed LCOE model or the fitness function is structured into four distinct modules as shown in Fig. 2(b). The first module deals with the farm layout, which has been adapted from the author's previous work and out of the scope of this paper. It employs a wake model to compute the wake loss of the farm layout. Additionally, it utilizes two sub-modules known as 'vessel routing' to determine the intra-array distance traveled by installation vessel during the installation processes using a GA, and 'cable routing' to find the optimum cable layout using Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP), for the optimized turbine locations. These data directly influence the CapEx, OpEx, and AEP modules described in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Capital expenditure (CapEx)

The capital expenditure includes the costs of getting permit requirements, site assessments and designing of the project, building the turbine components and their integration, turbine installation, grid connection, electricity generation, transmission, and distribution. While the component cost (c_i , where i is the component) is obtained by scaling the mass of each component with the rated power of the turbine, the installation cost (c_{ins}) is calculated by multiplying the day rate of the installation vessel by the total time required to finish the installation process. Details of mass scaling laws; and device, mooring system, and cable installation models will be published in a forthcoming journal paper. The model equations for the capital cost and its subcategories are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{device} &= c_{rotor} + c_{gen} + c_{shaft} + c_{bearing} + c_{ncl} + c_{nose} + c_{conv} + c_{trans} \\
 &+ c_{cool} + c_{control} + c_{cable} + c_{hub} + c_{brake} + c_{seals} + c_{buoy} \\
 &+ c_{tether} + c_{anchor} \\
 \bullet \text{ Device} & \\
 \bullet \text{ Subsystem} & \quad c_{subsys} = 0.10 \times c_{device} \\
 \text{integration} & \\
 \bullet \text{ Contingency} & \quad c_{contingency} = 0.10 \times \left(c_{device} + c_{subsys} + \frac{c_{ins}}{N} \right) \\
 \bullet \text{ Development} & \\
 \text{\& EC} & \quad c_{develop} = 0.11 \times (c_{device} + c_{subsys} + c_{contingency}) \\
 \bullet \text{ CapEx} & \quad CapEx = \left(c_{device} + \frac{c_{ins}}{N} + c_{subsys} + c_{contin} + c_{dev} \right) \times \left[N^{1 + \frac{\ln(1-LR_{CapEx})}{\ln(2)}} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, LR_{CapEx} represents the learning rate for capital cost which is considered to be 12% in the model.

2.2 Operational expenditure (OpEx)

The operational and maintenance costs include the cost of routine maintenance and the cost of major repairs. It also includes the cost of insurance. The total cost of parts replacement contains the cost of active parts replacement in the nacelle and the cost of mooring system replacement, respectively. The cost of repairing depends on the number of

interventions each year ($n_{intev/yr}$) and the operational cost per intervention (O_c). The cost factors f_{ncl} and f_{moor} , and $n_{intev/yr}$ are determined based on the failure rate of components. The following are the model equations for the operational cost and its subcategories:

- **Replacement**

$$c_{replace} = f_{ncl} \left(c_{rotor} + c_{gen} + c_{shaft} + c_{bearing} + c_{brake} + c_{seals} + c_{conv} \right) + c_{control} + c_{cool} + c_{trans}$$
- **Repair**

$$+ f_{moor} (c_{tether} + c_{anchor})$$

$$c_{repair} = n_{intrv/yr} \times O_c$$
- **Insurance**

$$c_{insure} = 0.01 \times \left(c_{device} + \frac{c_{ins}}{N} + c_{subsys} \right)$$
- **OpEx**

$$OpEx = (c_{replace} + c_{repair} + c_{insure}) \times \left[N^{1 + \frac{\ln(1-LR_{OpEx})}{\ln(2)}} \right]$$

Here, LR_{OpEx} represents the learning rate for operational cost which is considered to be 3% in the model.

2.3 Annual energy production (AEP)

The estimation of annual energy production involves calculating the efficiency (μ) based on different loss factors (L_i) and the availability of the turbines (A_v) and computing the power output of each turbine based on the frequency distribution of the current velocity (p), power coefficient (C_p), water density (ρ), front rotor radius (r_f), back rotor ratio factor (b), axial induction factor (a) and velocity (U_i). The model equations are as follows:

- **Efficiency**

$$\mu = (1 - L_g)(1 - L_{dt})(1 - L_w)(1 - L_e)(1 - L_o) A_v$$
- **Power output**

$$P = C_p \times \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi \sum p(U_i) [r_f^2 U_i^3 + b^2 r_f^2 (1 - 2a)^3 U_i^3]$$
- **AEP**

$$AEP = \mu \times \frac{365 \times 24}{1000} \times N \times P$$

3. Results and discussion

To test the functionality and rigorousness of the proposed LCOE optimization algorithm a 5 km × 5 km MHK farm is considered in the Gulf Stream 2.57 km off the coast of Florida at a depth of 50 m from the sea surface. The whole area of the farm is divided into 10 × 10 cells each cell having an area of 500 m × 500 m. Turbines are installed at a location that has a total depth of 800 m. The algorithm determines that a minimum LCOE of 0.058911 \$/kWh is obtained when 25 turbines are installed each having a diameter of 39.33 m.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3. (a) Convergence curves of the algorithm for 15, 25, 35, and 45 turbines as representatives; (b) Change of LCOE, turbine diameter, and wake loss with number of turbines; (c) Variation of capital cost, operational cost, and annual energy production for each turbine with its increasing number.

To provide clearer insights into the results, the LCOE model was executed separately for N values of 10 to 50 with an increment of 5. Fig. 3(a) depicts the convergence curves of the algorithm, with 15, 25, 35, and 45 turbines as representatives. It is evident that the algorithm converges before reaching 1000 generations for all cases.

In Fig. 3(b), we observe the variations in LCOE, the optimal turbine diameter, and the minimum wake loss in the farm with varying turbine numbers. As the number of turbines increases, the wake loss due to interactions also increases. However, to mitigate the possibility of these wake interactions, the optimum turbine size decreases. These opposing trends result in a concave LCOE curve, reaching its lowest point at $N = 25$.

Additionally, Fig. 3(c) presents how the three components of LCOE (capital cost, operational cost, and annual energy production) change with the increasing number of turbines. The power output experiences the highest rate of change, while the operational cost demonstrates the least variation.

Fig. 4. (a) Optimized farm layout for 25 turbines for minimum wake interactions; (b) Optimized vessel route travelled by the installation vessels for the optimized farm layout; (c) Optimal cable route for minimal cable cost for the same farm layout.

Figure 4(a) shows the optimized farm layout for 25 turbines for minimum wake interactions. The wake velocity is normalized with freestream velocity in the plot. Fig. 4(b) depicts the optimized vessel route travelled by the device installation vessel and the anchor handling vessel for the pre-optimized farm layout in Fig. 4(a). Fig. 4(c) illustrates the optimal cable route for minimal cable cost for the same farm layout.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study introduces an analytical model for estimating the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) for a marine hydrokinetic (MHK) farm comprising tethered coaxial dual-rotor turbines (TCDTs) anchored to the seabed. The model is employed in a bilevel optimization algorithm to determine the optimal size and number of turbines for achieving the minimum LCOE in a deployment location. The case study conducted in the Gulf Stream off the coast of Florida demonstrates the cost-effectiveness of installing 25 turbines with a diameter of 39.33 meters, resulting in an impressive minimum LCOE of 5.89 cents per kilowatt-hour. This research fills a gap in the evaluation of techno-economic feasibility for TCDTs and provides valuable insights for investors and developers considering the widespread commercial deployment of this promising marine hydrokinetic technology. The presented model and optimization algorithm offer a valuable tool for decision-making in the renewable energy sector and contribute to the ongoing efforts to combat climate change with sustainable energy solutions.

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